

Ayurvedic Approach for Managing Gout (*Vatrakta*): A Case Study

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Abstract:

Gout is a form of arthritis characterized by severe pain, redness and tenderness in joints. Data reveals that gout is more common in men than women, and its prevalence increases with age, and in some ethnic groups. The patient presented with complaints of redness, swelling and severe pain over both big toes of legs. His symptoms were treated using *Ayurvedic* measures and *Siravedh*. After a course of treatment lasting 3 months, follow up the symptoms were completely resolved. This case highlights the potential for *Ayurvedic* approaches in managing gout, offering an alternative to modern medicine.

Keywords: Gout, *Ayurvedic* treatment, *Vatrakta*, *Siravedh*, *Shaman Chikitsa*.

Introduction:

Gout is a form of inflammatory arthritis characterized by recurrent attacks of pain in red, tender, hot and swollen joint, ^[1] ^[2] caused by the deposition of needle like crystals of uric acid known as monosodium urate crystals. ^[3] At high levels, uric acid crystalizes and the crystals deposits in joints, tendons and surrounding tissues, resulting in an attack of gout. ^[4] As interest in holistic and alternative therapeutic approaches grows, more individuals are looking toward Ayurveda as a natural, non-invasive treatment. In Ayurveda it can be corelate with *Vatrakta*. *Vatrakta* is *vaat* and *rakta* (blood) *pradoshaja* disease and one of *Vataj* disease manifesting in *Sandhi* (joints), and the *dushyas* are *rakta*, *twaka* and *mansa* .^[5] It is subdivided mainly into *Uttana* and *Gambhir* types. It is also having 8 subtypes viz., *vataja*, *pittaja*, *kaphaja*, *raktaja*, *vaatapittaja*, *kaphapittaja*, *kaphavataja* and *Sannipataja*.^[6] This report presents a case in which an gout was successfully treated using *Ayurvedic* principles and therapies.

Aim: To manage gout using an *Ayurvedic* treatment protocol.

Description of patient:

- Name: XYZ
- Age: 48 years
- Gender: Male
- Occupation: Ex-service man
- Chief Complaints (*Vedana Vishesh*):
 - Redness over both big toes of legs (15 days)

- Severe pain in both big toes of legs (20 days)
- Tenderness and restricted movement over both toes of legs (20 days)
- Past Medical History:
 - No any history
 - No history of diabetes, HTN, thyroid disorders, or COVID-19.

Clinical Examination

Vital Signs:

- Blood Pressure: 110/90 mmHg
- Respiratory Rate: 22/min
- Temperature: 98.6°F
- Weight: 75 kg
- SPO2: 98% on room air

- ***Ashtavidha Parikshan:***
 - *Nadi: 76/min (Vata pittaja)*
 - *Mala: Samyak (1 veg/day)*
 - *Mutra: Samyak (4-5 times/day)*
 - *Jivha: saama*
 - *Shabda: Spashta*
 - *Sparsha: Samashitoshna*
 - *Druk: Prakrut*
 - *Aakruti: Prakrut*

Diagnosis (Ayurvedic Perspective):

According to *Ayurveda*, gout can be correlated with *Vatrakta* and it often caused by an *prakupita vaat* and *dushita rakta dosha* . Based on the patient's symptoms and physical examination, an *Ayurvedic* diagnosis of *vaataj vatrakta done*.

Treatment:

Sr no.	Medication	Dose	Anupana	Duration
1.	<i>Trayodashanga Guggul</i>	2 BD	<i>Koshna Jala</i>	21 days
2.	<i>Tab. Alurectic</i>	1 BD	<i>Koshna Jala</i>	21 days
3.	<i>Cap. Zeotone Plus</i>	1 BD	<i>Koshna Jala</i>	21 days
4.	<i>Avipattikara Churna</i>	1 tsp HS	<i>Koshna Jala</i>	21 days
5.	<i>Rasnasaptak Kwath</i>	2 teaspoon BD	<i>Koshna Jala</i>	21 days

Siravedha- *Siravedha* was done by scalp vein set.

- 2 setting of *Siravedha* were done in 30 days. One setting in 15 days.

Before Treatment: Uric acid value- 9.0 mg/dl

After Treatment: Uric acid value- 6.2 mg/dl

Results:

After 3 months of continuous *Ayurvedic* treatment the patient reported significant improvement in symptoms:

- Uric acid value decreased after the treatment.
- Redness and tenderness over both big toes was resolved.
- Pain over the affected area was resolved.

The patient was advised to continue the prescribed diet and lifestyle modifications for long term health maintenance.

Discussion:

This case shows that gout can be effectively managed with an *Ayurvedic* approach without the need of contemporary medicine. The patient was treated with *Ayurvedic Shaman Chikitsa* and *siravedh*. Gout is often caused by raised uric acid and characterized by severe pain, stiffness and difficulty in movement of small joints. In *Ayurveda*, gout is referred to as "*Vatrakta*," which is a *vataj* disease spreading in small joints. This case study aims to explore the effectiveness of *Ayurvedic* interventions in managing gout symptoms and improving patient outcomes.

In *Ayurveda*, gout is considered a manifestation of imbalances in the *doshas*, particularly *Vata* whereas involved *dushya* is *rakta*. The condition is often associated with an *vikruti* in *vata dosha*, leading to symptoms such as burning pain and inflammation in small joints. The treatment approach focuses on restoring balance through dietary changes, herbal remedies, and lifestyle modifications.

Conclusion:

Gout therapy with Ayurveda presents a viable alternative to traditional therapies. Ayurveda may speed up recovery and raise afflicted people's quality of life by treating the underlying cause and offering holistic treatment. To confirm these results and create uniform treatment methods, more research with bigger sample sizes and controlled procedures is crucial.

References:

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